

ISic3147

I.Sicily inscription 3147

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance

M. Pellegrino

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329959

1. δωχά-
2. ζου²⁶δοξάζου²⁶ πάντ[η] ἀέν ῶ
3. θεός.
- 4.

Edition: PHI329960

1. ΙϞS²⁶Iesus²⁶.
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645488

PHI 329959

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 18.0409

Bonacasa, N. 1955. Documenti cristiani sul Monte Pelligrino. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 31: 269-273. At ph

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